

Deliverable 7.1

Communication and Dissemination Plan

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Lead-beneficiary:	EUFIC
Work package Leader:	EUFIC
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1. Introduction

The FIT4FOOD2030 communication and dissemination plan sets out a strategy to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders. Importantly, the FIT4FOOD2030 consortium has been formed particularly with partners representing larger groups of organisations, so a significant emphasis will be put on tapping into the networks and communication channels that all project partners already have, through their membership base, newsletters, social media reach, etc. All partners are considered ambassadors of the project and are encouraged and expected to be involved to different degrees in communication and dissemination efforts.

2. Communication & dissemination strategy

The communication and dissemination plan addresses the following elements:

- Purpose (“why?”)
- Messages (“what?”)
- Key audiences (“who?”)
- Methods (“how?”)
- Time (“when?”)

Purpose (“why?”)

The overall aim of FIT4FOOD2030 is to support the European Commission (EC) with the development and implementation of the [FOOD 2030 research & innovation policy framework](#), to future-proof the European food systems. The main objective towards that, is to create a multi-stakeholder platform – the FOOD2030 Platform.

The FOOD2030 Platform connects stakeholders at multiple levels (cities/regions, countries, and Europe) so as to make Research & Innovation (R&I) policies on Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) more coherent, to build competences of current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers, and society at large, and to raise awareness of FOOD2030.

FIT4FOOD2030 takes a food systems approach and is built on the Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) concept, which is a dynamic, iterative process where all stakeholders involved in the R&I practice become mutually responsive and share responsibility regarding the RRI outcomes and process requirements. Therefore, it is key to ensure that all relevant stakeholders are well aware of the societal challenges addressed in FOOD 2030, the role of R&I therein, and what their potential involvement can be through RRI.

The communication and dissemination activities are part of Work Package 7 of the project and will be closely interlinked with Work Package 1 (Methodology to build the FOOD 2030 Platform), Work Packages 5 (Policy coherence and programme alignment: Policy Labs and EU Think Tank) and 6 (Building Competences on food system R&I and RRI: City Labs).

Messages (“what?”)

During the first phase of the project, the main FIT4FOOD2030 messages will be of a more general nature 1) to build the FIT4FOOD2030 ‘brand’, to create awareness of the project and its aims and to engage the relevant stakeholders, and 2) to promote the EC’s FOOD 2030 R&I policy framework.

Once the project starts to generate outputs, the general messages will be accompanied by specific messages promoting these and other activities, still with the aim to strengthen the FIT4FOOD2030 brand, and ultimately to increase the impact of the project and the FOOD 2030 R&I policy framework, including its priority areas.

As part of ‘building a brand’ that is recognised, a tagline has been created, which will be consistently mentioned when communicating about the project. The tagline is:

“Towards FOOD 2030 – future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation”

The **project phases** – Although the main aims of *building the brand, increasing visibility, and increasing the impact of FOOD 2030* will remain throughout the project, the content of the messages and target audiences may change slightly as the project phases evolve. Initial focus will be on the full range of possible stakeholders, with the outcomes of the visioning and interviews/workshops on current trends, showcases and breakthroughs as interesting messages to convey. As the project matures, the specific outcomes of the project will be disseminated in a more targeted way so as to ensure the highest impact, e.g. to support the ‘national transformation agendas’ created by the Policy Labs, to communicate best practices learnt along the way, and finally towards the sustainability of the FOOD 2030 Platform.

Key audiences (“who?”)

FIT4FOOD2030 aims to disseminate and promote awareness of the project and the FOOD 2030 policy framework to a wide range of stakeholders and audiences that relate to the food system, often requiring appropriate tailored presentation of information. In Table 1 the objective and approach is given per target audience.

Table 1. Target audiences and objective and approach of communication

Target audience	Objective	Approach
Citizens and consumers, CSOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the challenges facing our food systems, such as hunger, malnutrition, obesity, climate change, scarce resources, and waste. To increase awareness of their important role in setting the R&I agenda for FNS To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform To inform them on project outputs, e.g. food system trends and related R&I policy frameworks, best practices (showcases) and future R&I breakthroughs 	Policy/City Labs, website, social media, articles in non-specialised media (e.g. a EUFIC – and other partners’ – newsletter article)
School children and students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the challenges facing our food systems, such as hunger, 	City labs, social media, and (indirectly) through targeting

	<p>malnutrition, obesity, climate change, scarce resources, and waste.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the European food system, R&I, and FNS 	parents (see Citizens and consumers).
Knowledge and education centres (incl. researchers and teachers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the importance of the development of a shared strategic agendas across countries and alignment of research priorities. To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform 	Policy/city labs, website, social media, leaflets, newsletter.
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the importance of strategic alignment and policy coherence among Member States, so that R&I activities have maximum impact on local, regional or national FNS goals. To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform 	Policy/city labs, website, social media, newsletter
Businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the challenges facing our food systems, such as hunger, malnutrition, obesity, climate change, scarce resources, and waste. To increase awareness of their important role in setting the R&I agenda for FNS. To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform. 	Policy/city labs, website, social media, articles in non-specialised media (e.g. a EUFIC – and other partners’ – newsletter article).
Non-governmental organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the challenges facing our food systems, such as hunger, malnutrition, obesity, climate change, scarce resources, and waste. To increase awareness of their important role in setting the R&I agenda for FNS. To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform. 	Policy/City Labs, website, social media, articles in non-specialised media (e.g. a EUFIC – and other partners’ – newsletter article).
Funding agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the importance of strategic alignment and policy coherence among Member States, so that R&I activities have maximum impact on local, regional or national FNS goals. To engage them and encourage them to be part of the FOOD2030 Platform. 	Policy labs, website, social media, newsletter.

Method (“how?”)

Although EUFIC will coordinate the communication and dissemination activities, working closely with the project partners will be key to ensure that the maximum outreach, hence impact, is achieved. A process will be set up to disseminate project messages via the tools and channels of all partners. To support that, a detailed inventory (see table 2) will be created. This process entails the proactive communication with all organisations when articles/messages are ready to disseminate by EUFIC.

We recognize that the persons representing the organization in the project consortium are often not those responsible for communication within their organization. For that reason, as per table 1, we will aim to establish direct contacts by collecting contact details of those responsible for communication for each organization. Moreover, having ‘short lines’ of communication will allow us to be aware of the conferences/events that the partners are organizing/involved in, and when they happen, so as to prepare and align (social) media presence.

A non-exhaustive list of projects and networks reached through the project partners has already been collated at the proposal stage of the project and will be used as a starting point (Annex 1). Also the project’s external **Stakeholder Advisory Board (STAB)** and the **Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)** will be tapped into to disseminate project messages.

Table 2. Inventory (to be finalised) of FIT4FODO2030 project partners’ communication and dissemination tools and channels, for the purpose of ensuring the highest possible outreach.

Partner	Communications responsible	Newsletter (Y/N) & frequency	Recurrent deadline/when to contact?	Social media hashtags	Social media handles	Relevant recurrent/upcoming events?
VU	a.berkhout@vu.nl	N	?	#Athenalnsti te	Twitter: @VUAthenalnst FB: @AthenaVUAms terdam	Project events
HiOA						
AIT						
IrsiCaixa						
EUFIC	Raymond.gemen@eufic.org Joanna.kaniewska@eufic.org	monthly			@SciFoodHealth @EUFIC	
Ecsite						
JPI FACCE						
JPI OCEANS						
JPI HDHL						
ETP F4L						
ILSI						
PRIMA						
SUSFANS						
EIT FOOD						
MUFPP						

Partners’ dissemination activities may include but are not limited to: engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to EUFIC’s inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with EUFIC about project outputs, listing their own communication activities in a shared file, and providing translations of materials for non-scientific audiences in their local language. Where possible partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep EUFIC informed about their dissemination plans. Importantly, EUFIC is always available for ad hoc communication support.

To support and encourage partners’ involvement in communication activities, EUFIC will develop a ‘Communications guidance for all partners’.

A dedicated FIT4FOOD2030 Communications Working Group has been established (MS1) to ensure an efficient process of deciding on the projects visual identity as well as communications strategy and messages. The small group of partners, including representatives from VU, ILSI Europe, EIT Food, JPI HDHL and EUFIC, guarantees that different views and the specific needs of different stakeholders are incorporated in an efficient manner.

A recognisable project identity with logo and templates are essential for the branding of the project – the project logo has been created (figure 1), the templates are being finalised.

It has been decided, together with the EC, to stay close to the FOOD 2030 policy framework branding, so as to create a visual link to convey clearly that the consortium is working together with the EC, to give the project the required credibility and endorsement.

Figure 1. Project logo

An attractive, user-friendly project website (www.fit4food2030.eu) will be developed to increase the visibility of the project’s outputs to all target audiences. This website will be the main information resource for the project. Mutual links between the partners’ websites will drive traffic to the project website. The project website will contain:

- Details on the project aims & objectives, FOOD 2030 policy framework, project activities (including the upload of public deliverables in the respective relevant sections within this tab), partners, news, publications, contact details.
- Social media links/buttons.
- An interactive map to visualise the FOOD 2030 Platform.

A temporary website was created to support the early project activities.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the homepage of the temporary website.

A **communication campaign** will be organised to promote the **website launch**. This will be accompanied by an intensive social media presence for a number of days and a **press release** to attract media attention.

Social media will be used to share project messages and to redirect users towards the website. The EUFIC-managed Twitter account [Food Health Science](https://twitter.com/SciFoodHealth) (@SciFoodHealth) that brings the latest news from food and health related European research collaborations, will post content related to FIT4FOOD2030 regularly to increase outreach. Other partners will be encouraged to amplify posts from there. As it may be hard for partners to (remember to) be engaged in social media, they will be reminded regularly and small **social media trainings** will be held during the project meetings.

The hashtag, which was already created by the EC to support communications around FOOD 2030, for all social media posts will be **#FOOD2030EU**.

Although the project itself will not set up a dedicated Facebook, LinkedIn or other social media platforms besides Twitter, we will encourage the partners, including EUFIC, to use these channels for

dissemination. In this way we effectively tap into the already existing networks, rather than building up a social media following on new platform from scratch.

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the numbers, sources, types of content and individuals/organisations that promote or disseminate project messages, allowing optimisation and targeting of communication to ensure maximum outreach of news or results.

Printed material will be produced in the form of a bookmark explaining the project objectives and outcomes in accessible language, for distribution by partners at relevant events.

An **introductory PowerPoint presentation** will be created to support partners presenting about the project and to make sure that all partners speak about the project in a consistent manner, mentioning the same objectives and activities, and using the same terminology. Partners can then easily add slides setting out their own activities and contributions to the project.

An appealing and accessible bi-annual **e-newsletter** will be created and disseminated widely through the project's and partners' networks and communication channels.

Dissemination of project outputs will be enhanced by the publication of an **article in EUFIC's multi-lingual newsletter**.

An **infographic** will be developed (topic to be decided) to explain a complex issue in an understandable and engaging manner. The infographic will be widely promoted via ne2sletter and social media, always to increase the project's visibility.

A **high-level debate**, attracting high profile stakeholders from different disciplines (agriculture, food, health) addressing the main FOOD 2030 issues along the food chain, and two **scientific sessions**, at relevant scientific conferences, will be organised to disseminate project outputs and engage relevant stakeholders in the learning network with a long-term perspective.

A concluding **final conference** will be organised at the end of the project in Brussels to present the results to key target audiences: EC officers, opinion leaders/regulators, food manufacturers associations (including SMEs), retailers, consumer organisations, the media and the scientific community.

Time ("when?")

EUFIC will coordinate the project dissemination by providing updates on the project's website, e-newsletters, etc. EUFIC will play a proactive role in checking with partners for updates and news, thus ensuring the regularity of the flow of information. Contents resulting from project outcomes and other activities will be published online as they become available. At an early stage, when outputs are not yet available, EUFIC will actively seek for 'hooks' to promote the project, e.g. by communicating about the EC's activities around FOOD 2030 such as the publication of the conference report of the event on 16-17 October 2017 "Harnessing Research and Innovation for FOOD 2030: A science policy dialogue".

Also, of particular interest are the upcoming EU presidencies, and the respective countries/events will be targeted specifically, including the high-level FOOD 2030 event in Plovdiv, Bulgaria in June 2018.

Presence on social media started even before the project kick-off meeting and will be intensified after the website launch.

EUFIC and the other partners of the consortium will keep FIT4FOOD2030 in the public eye with both regular and special event activities that will run throughout the lifetime of the project.

Annex 1

List of selected important projects and networks with involvement of FIT4FOOD2030 partners:

Recent and ongoing projects and networks	Relation to the FIT4FOOD2030 proposal
FACCE JPI – Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change	Involved in the project via their secretariat INRA, which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
JPI OCEANS - Joint Programming Initiative on Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans	Involved in the project via their secretariat Research Council Norway, which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
JPI HDHL - Joint Programming Initiative on Healthy Diet for Healthy Life	Involved in the project via their secretariat Zorg Onderzoek Nederland, which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
SCAR - The Standing Committee on Agricultural Research	Connection to the SCAR working group on Food Systems, via INRA (chair working group), which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
PRIMA - Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area	Involved in the project via their secretariat University of Bologna, which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
ECSITE – European Network of Science Centers and Museums	Involved in the project as a partner
ETP Food for Life - European Technology Platform – Food for Life	Involved in the project via their secretariat FoodDrinkEurope, which is a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
EIT Food - European Institute of Innovation and Technology - Food (Public-private partnership)	Involved in FIT4FOOD2030 as a partner (as well as the Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC) on Food)
ILSI Europe - International Life Sciences Institute – Europe	Involved in the project as a partner (a scientific expert network on safe and nutritious food)
RRI TOOLS - Fostering Responsible Research and Innovation for society, with society (FP7)	Links via its partners VU, IrsiCaixa, which are also partner of FIT4FOOD2030
VOICES - Views, Opinions and Ideas of Citizens in Europe on Science on urban waste (FP7)	Linked via its coordinator Ecsite, and VU experts which are also partners of FIT4FOOD2030
SYNERGENE - Supporting Highly Adaptive Network Enterprise Collaboration through Semantically Enabled Knowledge Services (FP7)	Linked via project partners VU and Ecsite, which are also partners of FIT4FOOD2030
PLACES - Platform of Local Authorities and Communicators Engaged in Science (FP7)	Linked via its coordinator Ecsite, which is also a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
Connect4Action - Strategies for improving communication between social/consumer scientists, food technology developers and consumers (FP7)	Linked via its partner EUFIC, which is also a partner of FIT4FOOD2030
SEISMIC - Mobilising a wide range of urban stakeholders to feed experiences and challenges of social innovation at local level into the EU urban research agenda (H2020)	Linked via its partner AIT, which is also a partner of FIT4FOOD2030